

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Post-COVID-19 assessment of the use of Open Educational Resources at five European Library and Information Science higher education institutions [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

This article presents an analysis of the impact of Open Educational Resources (OER) during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as their potential use in the post-pandemic, in Library and Information Science (LIS) higher education institutions. The research explored how OER were used and created, what were the main barriers and drivers in practice and some main lessons learned that can help to improve the quality and increase the use of OER beyond times of crisis. The research was based on fieldwork carried out in the LIS departments of the universities of Barcelona (Spain), Hildesheim (Germany), Osijek and Zagreb (Croatia) and the University of Library Studies and Information Technologies in Sofia (Bulgaria). The methodology approach was qualitative and was based on interviews with faculty and focus groups with students. Results show that faculty members were still hesitant to adopt OER since they generally did not consider them. Moreover, those who did use them did so on their own initiative

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and as additional resources. We discuss the different speeds of OER implementation that have been observed depending on the faculty's prior level of knowledge, and on whether their institutions and countries are prepared to support the use of OER. The promotion of post-pandemic OER involves greater capacity building, as well as collaboration and institutional support. Students' attitudes about the usefulness of OER focus on their availability. The large number of teachers and students who participated in the study, as well as the international scope of the study, constitute a strength in the treatment of a topic such as the use of OER where the user perspectives and LIS context have been little addressed in the literature.

Plain language summary

Given that the period of the COVID-19 pandemic forced many universities to operate under an Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT) model, the use and creation of Open Educational Resources (OER) was supposed to be one of the best tools in the hands of teachers. However, the reality was quite different in many institutions as various barriers and constraints limited its use. The study of these circumstances in a period such as the pandemic allows us to identify the weaknesses and barriers that need to be taken into consideration in order to promote OER in the future, both in emergency situations and in normal teaching.

Keywords

Open Educational Resources (OER), Library and Information Science (LIS), Higher Education, COVID-19, Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT), Digital education.

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Introduction

The global COVID-19 pandemic impacted education in a disruptive way, forcing academics and students worldwide to adapt their courses to the online educational environment in a short time. This situation led to the adoption of more online resources than ever before; ranging from paid resources to commercial content that was temporarily available for free during the pandemic and Open educational resources (OER) (Schaffhauser, 2020; Stracke *et al.*, 2022).

OER are teaching and learning resources released under an open license and that can be reused, revised, and redistributed with no or few restrictions (UNESCO, 2019). In such an urgent transition during the pandemic to remote education, OER might be very important given their characteristics of openness, low cost, and flexibility. Moreover, they have the potential to transform teaching and learning to make these more accessible and equitable (Miao *et al.*, 2016). However, different conditions must coincide in the space and time to make them genuinely convenient and useful in a crisis of such magnitude. To help determine and examine the real impact and usefulness of OER, this article aims to contribute with a European case study based on the experience of five higher education institutions (HEIs) in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS).

OER initiatives during the pandemic

The pandemic increased awareness of the internationalization of educational resources, which led to the development of open education solutions and platforms and more sharing and use of OER around the world. There have been observed several cases, both at the institutional and national levels, of positive reactions to the COVID-19 lockdowns by implementing OER (UNESCO, 2022).

For instance, countries and HEIs with existing OER repositories or communities of practice based on the ideology of Open Education were better prepared for the emergency switch to remote education (Biernat *et al.*, 2020). In countries (such as in India, South Korea, and Sweden) some actions to provide OER training and support were developed, due to years of experience in distance learning systems. In Slovenia, formal support measures for developing digital resources were carried out, even before the pandemic (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2022). Canada, with a long tradition in supporting Open Education (OE), had several initiatives that supported OER use and adoption (McGreal, 2020).

There were also countries, such as China, Brazil and Indonesia, that had OER government-initiated and supported programmes (Huang *et al.*, 2020; Ossiannilsson *et al.*, 2020). One example of this is the governmental programme SPADA, which encouraged the development and dissemination of OER in more than 200 universities (Alhaj *et al.*, 2021).

At an institutional level, there are also examples of online universities (such as Athabasca University, Open University of the Philippines and Indira Gandhi International Open University) and others with previous experience in online

learning or open education (such as British Columbia) that were aware of OER and were using them during the pandemic (Arcebucho, 2022). Finally, a survey carried out by the European Commission (2020) in 114 HEIs revealed that open courses offered by massive open online courses (MOOCs) aroused great interest during the pandemic.

OER research during the pandemic

Research into the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic can be approached from different perspectives, (technological, sociological, emotional and economic). The one that we are specifically interested in within the scope of this study is how OER have been introduced and used to support emergency remote teaching (ERT) in higher education (HE).

In this sense, there are several reports from international organizations (European Commission, 2020; OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2022) that show worldwide examples of positive initiatives and changes in education as a reaction to the pandemic. There is also some collaborative research, based on analysing case studies in different countries (Biernat *et al.*, 2022; Bozkurt *et al.*, 2020; Ossiannilsson *et al.*, 2020; Stracke *et al.*, 2022), that provides a global outlook to assess the COVID-19 education crisis in relation to OER. While there were differences in country responses, researchers found that countries engaged similarly in terms of ERT.

A systematic review by Otto *et al.* (2021) provides evidence that the empirical research on OER is mainly focused on the use and adoption of the resources in HE, and that the research is located in North America. However, there are also some case studies from other geographies that are centred on the faculty's perspective regarding general awareness of OER (Biernat *et al.*, 2021; Christoforidou & Georgiadou, 2021; Watermeyer *et al.*, 2021) and attitudes to their use (Karatas *et al.*, 2022; Otto, 2022; Sunar *et al.*, 2022).

Likewise, there are some specific studies on the students' awareness. In this case, apart from a small number of projects that focused on students' perceptions of the usefulness of OER (Arcebucho, 2022; Cheung *et al.*, 2022), most have centred primarily on the students' attitudes towards technological change in education (Aguilera-Hermida, 2020; Händel *et al.*, 2022).

To address some of these gaps in prior literature, our research aims to contribute to the understanding of existing practices regarding the use of OER during the pandemic, specifically, in the case of academics and students from five European HEIs in the LIS discipline. This knowledge area is singularly interesting since there are few studies that directly address LIS context and those that do exist predate COVID-19 (Katz, 2020) or focus on parallel subtopics such as LIS training programs (Bell, 2021; Santos-Hermosa & Atenas, 2022) and the role of the librarians in OER (Kimball *et al.*, 2022).

Purpose and research questions

The value of this paper is that it not only identifies the main barriers, as well as the benefits of adopting OER but also highlights some real-life practical experiences of the contributions

and deficiencies of these resources during the ERT in the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, it also provides useful guidelines on how to effectively integrate OER beyond the pandemic period, based on these experiences. To explore and discuss all these issues, we established three research questions:

Q1: In what ways have OER been used and created for ERT during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Q2: What are the barriers and advantages of OER reported during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Q3: What are the main lessons learned during the pandemic that can help foster OER post-pandemic?

Methodology

To describe the design of the fieldwork and data analysis, we have checked it against the Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research (COREQ) (Tong *et al.*, 2007). In this section we present different aspects related to research team and reflexivity, study design and data analysis and reporting.

A qualitative approach has been adopted through semi-structured interviews with faculty and focus groups with students from four European countries of the five HEIs that are partners of the DECriS Erasmus+ Project. Content analysis was chosen as the theoretical framework to systematically organize data into a structured format through inductive open coding. Both, interviews and focus group methodologies, are well-established methodologies in educational science. While the first allows individuals to explain how they understand and interpret the world around a topic (Brinkmann & Kvale, 2018), the second provides interactions within a group and generates both different and common feedback and ideas (Smithson, 2000).

During the first four-month period of 2022, a total of 39 interviews with faculty and 10 focus groups with a total of 47 students were carried out, both face-to-face and online, depending on the COVID-19 situation or the participants' preference. No one else besides the participants and researchers was present during the interviews and focus groups.

The interviewers and moderators of the focus groups were part of the working teams from each of the institutions participating in the DECriS project. They were all faculty from these institutions and received specific training in order to take consistent testimonies from the 5 institutions where the fieldwork was carried out. They were all familiar with the context and the profiles of the interviewees, given that they belonged to the same institution. The interviewees were well informed about the DECriS project and the research objectives. The fact that the interviewers and interviewees belonged to the same institution was an advantage, as there was a common basis of knowledge of the context of each of the institutions. On the other hand, this familiarity between interviewers and interviewees may have been a limitation in terms of the way in which interviewees expressed their experiences and opinions.

The breakdown of participants by partner can be seen in Table 1. Throughout the paper, all the quotes from the interviews are labelled with the partner code followed by the interview number (e.g., [OJ_1] for Osijek teacher #1); for focus groups we added the letters FG before the number (e.g., [OJ_FG_1] for Osijek focus group #1).

As we used two qualitative techniques that involved a relatively small number of people compared to the total teacher and student populations, it was necessary to determine the criteria and the sampling system to decide who would be interviewed and who would be part of the focus group meetings. Therefore, the purposive sampling technique (i.e., non-probabilistic sampling) was applied under the knowledge that each partner had of the context of their participants. To simplify the conduct of the interviews and focus groups, once the criteria and the sampling routine had been established, each partner institution made its choice of people considering that it was necessary to ensure that the samples had the appropriate representation regarding the different students' levels and teachers' subject domains. The following criteria were applied:

- Bachelor's and master's degree faculty and students of various courses who were teaching or enrolled during the pandemic period of lockdowns (2020-2021).
- Parity between genders and age groups was respected both for the participants of the interviews and the focus groups.

In compliance with the COREQ guidelines for interviews and focus groups, our research prioritized ethical considerations. Written informed consent was diligently obtained, ensuring participants understand the study's purpose. Stricter measures, including interviewees quotations anonymization at the results outputs and secure data storage, were implemented to guarantee confidentiality. The design of the study, as well as the process of data collection and its safekeeping, was approved, on 2021-11-05 by the Bioethics Commission of the University of Barcelona (CBUB) [Institutional Review Board (IRB00003099) <http://www.ub.edu/comissiobioetica/en>], as

Table 1. Number of interviews and focus groups held by all partners.

Partner	Interviews	Focus Group (Students)
Barcelona [BA]	14	2 (10)
Hildesheim [HI]	3	2 (9)
Osijek [OJ]	9	1 (6)
Sofia [SO]	8	4 (16)
Zagreb [ZA]	5	1 (6)
Total	39	10 (47)

the Barcelona team led the IO-2 workpackage of the DECriS Project.

The interviews and focus groups were conducted and audio-recorded, following common guidelines (Urbano *et al.*, 2024), by each education institution in the native languages of their respective countries (Bulgarian, Catalan, Croatian, German, and Spanish). The audio recordings were transferred to the Barcelona team to carry out an automatic transcription, which was subsequently edited, listening to the original audio and translated into English by each of the participating teams. During the editing and translation process, the most important phrases and key concepts were highlighted by each partner team, to guide the coding work by the Barcelona team who consolidated the report on the interpretation of the results. Qualitative data analysis software, Atlas.ti, facilitated the management and analysis of interview and focus groups transcripts. With all the text files in English, the Barcelona team worked on the inductive coding (Mayring, 2010) of all the transcriptions and data analysis to produce the preparation of the reports of each centre and the final joint report. The analysis was double-checked by a researcher of each partner to avoid bias or misunderstandings. The questionnaire script used in the interviews and focus groups was structured, in both cases, into six main thematic sections with a total of 38 questions which is also included in the Mayring approach (Boté-Vericad *et al.*, 2022; Braun & Clarke, 2006). While this guide covered a wide range of topics, aligned with the overall objectives of the DECriS project, this paper focuses

specifically on the topic referring to the real situation and perception of OER. The resulting coding scheme used for reporting this specific OER section of the DECriS Intellectual Output-2 can be seen in Table 2.

Results

OER use and creation

In terms of how the OER were used, faculty reported that they adapted previous materials to the online environment and that some of them also used OER as additional or supplementary material. They specified that they used open resources from others (such as videos, TED talks, MOOCs, etc) and resources in the public domain, as can be seen in the interview extracts below.

“I have used some of them [OER], but they were not my own resources. I've already forgotten what they're called – a kind of online university where you have MOOCs”. [HI_8]

“I use mostly video materials because I think the students are already reading enough written texts. They were mostly video lectures that were in the public domain or available openly on different channels like YouTube” [OJ_6]

“[Looking for OER] Well, maybe some videos, or some TED talks that I later asked the students to comment on, or I would ask them questions related to the videos.” [ZA_5]

Table 2. Traced occurrences for “OER” codes.

Code	Subcode	Category
Adaptations (AD)	AD01	Approaches to emergency remote teaching
	AD04	Supplementary materials provided by teachers (*)
	AD05	Looking for new educational resources and use of OER
	AD06	Creation of OER
	AD08	Production of videos or voice clips other than recorded live lectures
Problems (PR)	PR06	Not a good time to create new material from scratch purposely designed
	PR08	Access to library resources and copyright problems
Advantages (AV)	AV04	Promotion of the creation and reuse of educational resources
Improvements (IM)	IM03	Promotion and support for improving OER use and creation
	IM05	Teachers' training and mindset change
	IM08	Improvement of the students' workload estimation when planning courses (*)
	IM15	Strengthening the role and resources of libraries and support services for teachers

Note: Those categories with (*) refer just to students

It stands out that, while in some cases the faculty verified the terms of use of the material and whether it was available under the open licence, in others they did not:

“I approach these resources very carefully [...] I avoid using resources directly without checking the status of the material.” [SO_7]

“I developed presentations, especially for online learning, in which I put links to access various interactive applications as additional materials with open access. I didn't check whether the resources are licensed or open for use, but after they were uploaded for free access on the Internet, I assumed that training resources were open.” [SO_8]

In addition, it has been observed that some faculty members also introduced GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) resources into their teaching, although it is not clear whether these were OER or non-OER (i.e. with subscription or not under open licences or as public domain with clearly labelled).

“I especially warn my students to be very careful when using Internet resources and direct them to verified sources. I advise them to use the opportunities offered by libraries and museums.” [SO_7]

“Because knowledge exists to spread, I also introduced materials and resources provided by various Bulgarian institutions - libraries, archives, museums, etc., as well as promoted access to the digital library of the University, which we created in connection with the pandemic and its consequences.” [SO_8]

On the other hand, some students reported that they turned to YouTube on their own for additional help, from tutorials for instance, to fill the gaps in the faculty's guidance:

“... if we passed the subject, it was because of the YouTube tutorials not because of the teacher. So, you couldn't record his class to follow it as a tutorial, you couldn't do the exercises while he was doing them because you'd miss what he was doing on the screen.” [BA_FG_1]

Concerning OER creation, faculty said that they produced short videos to clarify very specific issues or to give instructions on installing and using software, using information resources, etc. The online environment also led to more project-based learning activities and gamification resources being developed.

“It's a lot of work to record them [videos] and it took a long time. [...] But of course, you have to think about the fact that you can reuse them” [HI_4]

“We actually developed some virtual projects. For example, a virtual museum of students and their works in publishing, where they were very engaged.” [OJ_2]

Another phenomenon observed in the interviews is that although the faculty endorsed the OER philosophy, their

productions were not always conceived as such - they did not label them as OER or consider they had OER characteristics.

“I'm not sure to what extent [I created OER], because, of course, personal experiences are one thing, yes, and the possibility of exchanging [teaching experiences], creating Creative Commons materials, for example, and having them available in a community of users, is another. [BA_8]

In addition, it seems there was not a formal way to integrate OER due to the costs of a more elaborate preparation for the public presentation of materials and the creator's belief that the resource is not good enough or not fully finished; as well as challenges related to licensing, depository, indexing, etc.

“My only concern [creating OER] is that it's not the best quality. And then I think it would be stupid if someone uses it and then is somehow disappointed [...]. So if it didn't cost anything, I would probably say, well, don't cry, if something doesn't work, it's free. But then I would have it. I would like to have it in such an optimal condition, which of course would require a lot of work and refinement.” [HI_4]

Opposing positions can be seen regarding the suitability of the pandemic times for creating OER. Some faculty members stated that it was not a good time to create new material from scratch designed for a specific purpose, since the course was ongoing and was not planned to be carried out in a crisis situation, such as the ERT.

“I didn't create new materials so as not to change the students' work dynamics too much. In fact, we tried to work much harder to support these materials than to create new ones.” [BA_10]

Others, however, considered that some experiences and resources used during the health crisis stimulated the creation of materials, some of which may continue to be useful in the return to a more normal situation beyond COVID-19.

“I kept all the materials somewhere in my archive, so in case we had to teach online again some time, then I could access the materials again. [...]” [OJ_4]

Barriers to OER

Some of the main problems that faculty reported were about OER concern findability issues, the lack of knowledge or awareness about OER and the lack of OER other than foreign language resources.

In terms of the problem of finding OER, we observed that some faculty searched for OER with the aim of facilitating more dynamic and autonomous learning, but they were not successful. They considered that this was because there were not enough repositories of OER, there was no specific content ready for teaching and currently there is not a culture of sharing:

“This is about looking for other digital materials... In fact, I had already looked for them before [the pandemic],

but I hadn't managed to find them. [...] We should have more repositories of materials that are useful to us... [the problem is that] we don't share them, or we don't know how to find them." [BA_12]

"I had problems finding some of the materials and resources that I could use [...] I think we should have more repositories of OER and different digital materials that are available to use so there are more in the public domain or licenced through Open Licencing by CC. And I think we should be more open to sharing resources. We talk about open science and open education, but in practice we don't see it so much." [OJ_6]

Searching for videos and online material available in open access, not previously used in face-to-face teaching, has been identified as an important trend among some faculty to adjust their teaching planning. While some did not find enough online bibliography and digital material openly available, others found videos on YouTube or TED talks from key authors whose books and articles they had recommended in the subject bibliography.

"I looked for more bibliography online, [a search] that I might not have done in the case of normal face-to-face teaching." [BA_1]

"I am currently preparing a new subject. I listen to these video lessons by Russian colleagues, as well as North American ones, because I have their books. I have downloaded them for free, there is free access, but I saw that they also had these video lessons that were available on YouTube." [SO_11]

"I use open access platforms such as TED and YouTube, where the authors have voluntarily provided their materials for free use. I encourage students to use the opportunities of libraries and museums, which provide virtual tours, digital collections and online information services." [SO_7]

In terms of not knowing about or being aware of OER, the express creation of OER was absent in most of the faculty' discourses and reflections. Faculty did not differentiate between open digital materials and the educational resources that correspond strictly to the set of characteristics that define OER.

One of the weaknesses of OER identified through the interviews was that they are not part of faculty' mental framework. Faculty do not know their distinctive characteristics or the repositories in which to locate them and how to evaluate them. In some cases, in which OER were specifically mentioned, faculty said that the ones they found did not fit what they really needed. It is observed that most of them had a fuzzy idea of what OER are and where to look for them.

"I've probably used them [OER]. Yes, when I used them, I was interested, but now I can't say anything specific." [SO_2]

"Probably the first thing that came to my mind was that I probably didn't even think that there could be anything relevant to my course, since the topic is quite specific, but I don't know." [ZA_1]

"I suppose that faculty should investigate the OER available to make more use of the resources that already exist out there ... But, of course, you start searching from your personal experience of contents created for a face-to-face class. Finding equivalents that refer to that exact content is very difficult." [BA_1]

The lack of knowledge that has been identified is also linked to a lack of time to look for new solutions or to adapt existing ones.

"It's hard for me to find things that are useful. You spend a lot of time looking and what I find isn't much...I think that the idea of OER is very good, but in practice it's hard for me to apply it." [BA_12]

Finally, the lack of non-English OER or availability in multiple foreign languages are other barriers that faculty report.

"The problem is that they [OER] are in English. Yes, there are opportunities for automatic translation, but the quality is not good enough. A big problem with my subjects is that there are no similar materials for the Bulgarian archival institutions." [SO_4]

Benefits of OER

Some faculty members pointed out that some of the main advantages of OER are that they encourage and foster reusability of materials, that they can be adapted and enriched, and they are available and accessed quickly:

"Another interesting topic when educational materials are adapted for online teaching is that it encourages and fosters reusability of materials. So, if you can reuse it, then I can also be sick for a week and just upload it." [HI_4]

"The main advantages of the OER that I would point out are the fast access and that is easy to make changes. I can edit something, I can add, enrich, adapt the resource. They are available from anywhere at any time." [SO_1]

"I have always believed that what I develop for my courses should be accessible to a wider range of users; so, yes, this was always my attitude. And now the pandemic has intensified this feeling and I think it would be good to work towards creating OER in Bulgarian." [SO_6]

Although there is no evidence whether students are referring to OER or general digital resources, they express a need for some kind of material that they can reuse asynchronously outside the classroom for self-paced learning, to adjust their learning paths, and for clarification, etc.

"Prof. xx pre-recorded her lectures, so we could listen to them whenever we wanted. The great thing about it is

that you can go back to it and listen to the lecture as much as you want.” [OJ_FG_1]

“Apart from googling and searching for materials when we need to find additional information or clarify something we didn’t understand, I haven’t used any special tools like this [OER], except for normal databases, articles and similar things.” [ZA_FG_1]

Needs and requirements to foster OER: lessons learned

Throughout the interviews, it was observed that there have been few approaches to ERT that involved OER, and these have differed among DECriS partners. Most faculty stated that they modified their materials to make them more compatible with the online environment, but there was little emphasis on specifically including OER. However, there were some cases of institutions and faculty who were more familiar with e-learning (since they had previous experiences and a positive attitude) and were therefore more likely to use OER and implement them in their teaching practice.

The focus groups revealed that although students were happy with the availability of more digital resources, they wanted the teaching of the subjects to be planned better and for the pedagogical practices to be more innovative.

In this diverse scenario caused by the pandemic, some lessons were learned about what requirements were necessary to promote OER beyond the crisis. According to faculty, a change in mindset and more awareness, together with more training and new skills, were some of the necessary conditions. Although institutions offered training courses, they were more related to the features of the Moodle platform associated with active teaching and educational technology, rather than specifically on creating and using OER.

“Everyone needs new competencies. So, faculty’ competencies are very low.” [OJ_2]

“Perhaps it would not be a bad idea to offer some kind of education in general on producing new teaching materials. So that each teacher can choose what suits them.” [OJ_1]

“I have the feeling that it is difficult to deviate from it or to try something new, and we’re going through a period of upheaval [...]. Something is changing, simply because many new, younger faculty are coming in who are also willing to try something new.” [HI_8]

“We should work more on building awareness around OER. Because I think it’s a general problem, so people aren’t producing or using OER enough.” [OJ_6]

During the interviews, other needs also came up, such as the creation of a catalogue, a guide, or a list of quality teaching material for the different subjects, as well as tools to be able to use the technology better (videos, subtitles, etc.). With a

few exceptions, faculty also indicated the lack of centralized support and resources from their institutions and how an improvement in this support and more collaboration could benefit the use of OER. For example, it would be useful to have directives, to share good practices and solutions to problems experienced while using tools and have more resources and digital platforms.

“[We need] more technical directives about tools, less dispersion.... less "do it yourself"[...] more centralized [support is needed], more training for faculty on resources to work online with a different model of courses.” [BA_14]

“I think it [fostering OER creation] should come from the top, I mean, the university is still a very hierarchical system, and as long as there is no directive from the top that says we want to do this, it’s difficult.” [HI_8].

Discussion

The faculty interviewed mostly reported that they did not use OER because they were not familiar with the term, OER were difficult to locate, or they did not consider it relevant (because of the language or because they were not ready for specific teaching or discipline needs). However, those who did use OER generally did it as an individual initiative (not supported by the institution) and as additional or supplementary material within their teaching.

Our findings on the barriers to using OER show that they are aligned to other studies. More specifically, the lack of awareness about OER (Seaman & Seaman, 2017) and the legal uncertainty (Otto *et al.*, 2021) have been found to be the major obstacles to using OER. In this respect, a related key aspect emerged from our results and present in other literature is the urgent need for professional development and training for faculty (Santos-Hermosa & Atenas, 2022; Stracke *et al.*, 2022), as well such as not focus on the use of e-learning tools but rather on how to create open content (Nabukeera, 2020).

Moreover, the findability problem connected to the experiences of it being time-consuming to locate relevant OER in different repositories was also a common impediment reported by faculty (Biernat *et al.*, 2022; Otto *et al.*, 2021), despite the growing number of OER in repositories (Santos-Hermosa *et al.*, 2021). As there is no centralized infrastructure for sharing OER, which has been reported as a widespread problem worldwide (Stracke *et al.*, 2022), one possible measure would be to have a meta-searcher (Otto *et al.*, 2021) to facilitate access from one single platform. In this sense, LIS professionals (both faculty-students binomial and academic libraries) might have a critical role in strengthening action plans and infrastructures to ensure the discoverability of OER.

LIS faculty also stated that the lack of OER for specific topics or perspectives, and the lack of culturally or linguistically tailored OER, were other issues that contribute to these

resources not being used. This specificity can be seen as a paradox since the potential of OER is precisely the flexibility to be adjusted locally and globally. OER have the advantage that faculty can adapt them to their own context to maximize student engagement and promote diverse learning experiences (Van Allen & Katz, 2020). In any case, our findings are aligned to Koseoglu *et al.* (2020), who note a lack of OER development in non-English languages and the need for local OER to fit the learners' contexts and represent proximity perspectives. Results also underline the need to have subject-specific OER in the LIS discipline, in accordance with the study by Christoforidou and Georgiadou (2021), which reports that the lack of a portal that accommodates OER for Arts Graphics is one of the biggest obstacles to the use of OER.

However, DECriS LIS institutions also highlighted some advantages of using OER, both from the point of view of academics and students. Faculty perceived OER as being easy to reuse, adapt, and access quickly. These are, in fact, some of the best-known benefits of OER, as CC licenses (depending on the type) give permission to modify the content to create new OER that are culturally relevant and inclusive for different contexts and learners (Van Allen & Katz, 2020). Students also appreciated OER, due to the immediacy and usefulness of digital materials (such as tutorials) and their availability outside the classroom. Likewise, Cheung *et al.* (2022) found that students generally consider OER useful as supplementary course materials or to help them to understand concepts. Angelopoulou *et al.* (2022), who studied student feedback on the use of open textbooks, concluded that students with higher motivation to learn perceived this kind of OER as a better option than the traditional textbook in comparison to less motivated students.

It should be noted that students in our research seem to understand OER more as digital resources available online rather than specific open learning material. The study of Arcebuche (2022) also identified that students associated OER with videos, images, e-books and other online resources that they could usually access through webpages, wikis, web engines and YouTube.

Regarding the creation of OER, DECriS LIS institutions do not exhibit much evidence either. Those faculty who produced them did it in the form of video, project-based materials and gamification resources. Nevertheless, these resources were often not conceived as OER; that is, they did not have the key characteristics of assigning open licenses, or sharing them openly by depositing them into a repository, etc. Therefore, some of the new resources created seem to be more innovation educational materials rather than OER. These results are also consistent with the findings of other authors (Biernat *et al.*, 2022; Kurt, 2019; Sunar *et al.*, 2022), which indicates that academics are confused about open licenses, and that they use and create OER under misconceptions or without knowing the theoretical concept about them. On the other hand, there are other studies about OER in the times of COVID-19 that show the creation of some instructional videos designed

specifically as OER; in the sense that they are open for reuse and enable student engagement and accessibility (Boté-Vericad & Miguillón, 2012; Doi *et al.*, 2022).

All these practices of OER use and creation identified among LIS academics and students evidence a limited readiness for OER implementation during the COVID-19 pandemic. The European Commission (2020) also identified this aspect in a survey among different HEIs on how they could have been better prepared to face the pandemic. Alhaj *et al.* (2021), also reported that the unpreparedness of institutions and their teaching staff has led in many cases (in North America and Europe) to poor quality ERT rather than well-constructed online learning. Similar results were informed in Turkey (Sunar *et al.*, 2022), where HEIs were found to be unprepared for online education, with faculty and students lacking the necessary digital skills.

In our study, LIS institutions have mainly focused on tools and workspaces for distance education but have not explored the further possibilities offered by digital OER. The online environment has helped to innovate education and to develop some project-based learning. However, since it is needed a certain shift in mindset and an investment of time for designing and implementing OER, the ERT period caused by the COVID-19 pandemic does not seem to have been the most appropriate time for doing this. Our faculty reported that e-learning and teaching require working on a more carefully constructed and detailed teaching plan and resources. Therefore, for those institutions that were transitioning to online education and becoming familiar with OER for the first time, it seems that the pandemic was not a good time to create new and purposely designed resources from scratch.

This overall scenario shows that the pandemic has been a catalyst for digital transformation in HEIs around the world. The online environment has helped to innovate education and to develop some project-based learning. However, the ERT period caused by the COVID-19 pandemic does not seem to have been the most appropriate time for doing this. According to Alhaj *et al.* (2021), the unpreparedness of institutions and their teaching staff has led in many cases (in North America and Europe) to poor quality ERT rather than well-constructed online learning. Our faculty reported that e-learning and teaching require working on a more carefully constructed and detailed teaching plan and resources. Therefore, for those institutions that were transitioning to online education and becoming familiar with OER for the first time, it seems that the pandemic was not a good time to create new and purposely designed resources from scratch.

However, there were diverse contexts and experiences depending on the inequalities and different levels or speeds that have been observed in some countries and educational institutions. While some HEIs are in their infancy stage regarding awareness and engagement with OER and OEP, as we have observed in DECriS LIS institutions, other HEIs have an established culture of OER that has been further strengthened

with the COVID-19 educational response. Some of the drivers have been the development of technological infrastructure as well as policies and strategies for a greater engagement with OE (Bozkurt *et al.*, 2020; Ossianilsson *et al.*, 2020; Nagashima & Hrach, 2021).

In this regard, the UNESCO (2019) Recommendation on OER also echoes the need to improve some of the aspects mentioned above through its areas of action, such as those of building capacity of stakeholders (i), developing supportive policies (ii) or encouraging the creation of inclusive and equitable quality OER (iii).

Conclusions

a) The impact of OER during COVID on the LIS HEIs analyzed in our research has not been strong, as they are in an early stage of OER implementation

In this study, we have seen that there are different paces of OER implementation in HEIs around the world. In the case of the LIS institutions in our research, they are mainly in a first stage of the process of adopting OER, which, according to Kaminski's (2011) theory of diffusion of innovations, would correspond to the "Knowledge or Awareness" level. As a result, there would still be several implementation stages to go through before shifting from early awareness to full-fledged OER adoption.

This point is especially relevant in the case of the LIS discipline, since the scope of knowledge of LIS faculty is directly related to OER, in terms of their mission of providing access to information for all. Therefore, OER-specific programmes an open educational practice could be introduced into the LIS teaching, which would benefit faculty and students as well as set an example for other disciplines and university communities.

b) OER have been used and created in different ways during the COVID-19 pandemic, depending on the level of awareness (Q1)

In general, there is little awareness about the role and impact that OER can have in education, especially in crisis situations. LIS faculty were not very familiar with OER in terms of how to create them or where to find them, nor with the use of the open licenses. However, they showed a good attitude towards using some OER as additional learning resources and towards the innovative creation of more interactive materials. As some OER solutions that faculty used during the pandemic as an "experimental approach" have worked well, now would be the time to develop a consistent teacher training programme.

From the students' perspective, it seems that OER will continue to evolve as an important source of learning materials, as students were especially pleased with the accessibility and reusability of the resources, and they recognized the benefits of using complementary and specialized resources. Although students were not particularly aware of OER during the

pandemic, they seem now to recognize their usefulness more than before.

c) The barriers and advantages of OER reported during COVID-19 are consistent with other previous literature (Q2)

This study, situated in the specific field of LIS, mirrors the results of OER adoption studies in other fields. In any case, this research emphasizes two main aspects: the lack of knowledge about OER and their characteristics and the findability problem with OER scattered across different sources, which are mostly unknown to users. Since being familiar with OER positively affects attitudes towards them, faculty who are unaware of OER are likely to be slow to adopting them and will use OER for supplemental purposes in their courses. Moreover, the fact that many faculty used YouTube as a key source for locating videos to include in their lessons, demonstrates the importance of effective discovery mechanisms and the need for more training in OER and specialized sources.

d) Some of the main lessons learned that will help to foster OER post-pandemic (Q3) are the need to learn new skills, have more training and have more collaboration and institutional support

Capacity building in OER, as well as know-how to create them and relevant sources to share them, are necessary for them to become generalized. In addition, more collaboration and institutional support are required, both in terms of centres and departments involved (faculty, libraries, educational innovation, etc.), as well as strategies and rewards to foster OER.

Regarding interdepartmental collaboration, LIS faculty could create and employ OER more widely by relying on and working together with their academic libraries, which often stand out by leading or supporting the OER movement. As for the contribution of libraries, it can range from providing library materials for OER creation, selecting existing OER for use, and providing infrastructure (repositories and other platforms), to involving library staff directly in OER development and academic support. In this regard, LIS discipline could be helpful in OER context due to the experience of its professionals (academics and librarians) and their specialization in searchability, repositories management and the ability to identify thematic OER.

Ethics and consent

In compliance with the COREQ guidelines for interviews and focus groups, our research prioritized ethical considerations. Written informed consent was diligently obtained, ensuring participants understand the study's purpose. Stricter measures, including interviewees quotations anonymization at the results outputs and secure data storage, were implemented to guarantee confidentiality. The design of the study, as well as the process of data collection and its safekeeping, was approved, on 2021-11-05 by the Bioethics Commission of the University of Barcelona (CBUB) [Institutional Review Board (IRB00003099)

<http://www.ub.edu/comissibioetica/en>], as the Barcelona team led the IO-2 workpackage of the DECriS Project.

Data availability

Underlying data

Due to the sensitive nature of the research and the legal restrictions agreed with the Bioethics Commission of University of Barcelona-CBUB [Institutional Review Board (IRB00003099) <http://www.ub.edu/comissibioetica/en>] the supporting data (audio recordings and transcriptions) is not available. The consent of the participants in the interviews and focus groups was obtained under this condition.

However, a fairly complete selection of anonymised excerpts from interviews and focus groups is available as quotations embedded at the complete analysis of the responses that can be found at the Intellectual Output-2 report of the DECriS Project, uploaded to the institutional repository of the University of

Barcelona: <http://hdl.handle.net/2445/201761> (This report is a working paper and was not peer reviewed).

Extended data

Figshare: DECriS Project Intellectual Output 2: Qualitative Research Instruments. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25541524.v1>

This project contains the following extended data:

- Guide for teachers' interviews
- Students' focus groups moderator guide

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our sincere gratitude to all the team members from the five DECriS project partners.

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 02 July 2024

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Som Nath Ghimire

Nepal Open University, Lalitpur, Nepal

First of all, I would like to congratulate the authors for their contribution to the literature associated with Open Educational Resources (OER), which warrants a continued examination in higher education. I am particularly interested in reviewing this paper to know to what extent the COVID-19 pandemic prompted the wider understanding, creation, and implementation of Open Educational Resources in Library and Information Science (LIS) within higher education institutions in the countries under the study scrutiny. Having reviewed the paper, I suggest improvements in the following areas so that the rigor of the paper could be significantly strengthened.

1. Reconsider the title of the paper since the significant data collected and utilized are related to the faculty membersâ and studentsâ narratives and reflections on OER implementation during the COVID-19 contexts although the respondents were interviewed during the post-pandemic situation.
2. Both the introduction and literature review sections would further benefit if the authors could substantially revise these sections with updated literature in the area under scrutiny.
3. In so doing, please review past and recent literature that principally agrees with the widely accepted definition of OER rather than solely relying on UNESCO's (2019) definition. Consider, if there are any disagreements regarding the concept of OER over the years.
4. The review section is poorly written and the line of reasoning for the current research is less than satisfactory. Please consider critically reporting the theoretical arguments and empirical research findings to set the broader context for the current research under scrutiny. This section could further benefit if the authors focus on reviewing literature in the areas associated with their research questions so that it would logically connect with the findings and discussion section.Â Moreover, the literature section seems to have abruptly ended, which looks very odd. I suggest that the authors summarize the literature review in a short paragraph and show the research gap that warrants further examination.
5. In the methodology section, I wonder why the authors have not considered it important to give information about the participants, whether all of them belong to Library and Information Science or different departments. Unclearly about the details could further mislead the readers since the title of the paper and abstract are centered around this information. It is equally absent in the analysis section though the authors have mentioned

this information in the discussion and conclusion section that the participants belonged to LIS. Â

6. In the findings and analysis section, the paper could further benefit from a critical interpretation of data, which the paper hugely lacks in its current form. Also, I believe that the inverted commas in the quotes should be removed with the indentation the journal requires.
7. Equally important concerns for me are that since the research has been based on fieldwork carried out in the LIS departments of the universities of Barcelona (Spain), Hildesheim (Germany), Osijek and Zagreb (Croatia) and the University of Library Studies and Information Technologies in Sofia (Bulgaria), there might be different experiences and perception of faculties and students toward OER based on their contexts. If authors have something interesting to share (probably not reported in the available literature as well as that has not been highlighted with clarity (compare and contrast) in the current study), I would encourage the authors to equally highlight these findings and discuss them. I believe that it would have a greater implication in the literature as well as guide future debates in the area.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Higher education; technology in education; online and distance education; integrity; academic dishonesty; surveillance; discourse studies; gender studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Jul 2024

Cristóbal Urbano

We the authors greatly appreciate the reviewers' comments and time. Based on their suggestions, we will answer the reviewer's observations and revise our paper over the next few weeks to submit a new, corrected version. Some of the team members involved in this paper will be on holiday for a few weeks, so it will take some time. Thank you for your patience. Sincerely, Cristóbal Urbano, corresponding author

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Author Response 28 Aug 2024

Cristóbal Urbano

We would like to thank reviewer 2 for the helpful comments and suggestions on our manuscript. It is with great pleasure that we upload a revised version. The response to each comment is detailed below, together with the changes we have made to version 2 of the paper where appropriate (new text can be seen through the tracked changes):

- **Comment #0:** *First of all, I would like to congratulate the authors for their contribution to the literature associated with Open Educational Resources (OER), which warrants a continued examination in higher education. I am particularly interested in reviewing this paper to know to what extent the COVID-19 pandemic prompted the wider understanding, creation, and implementation of Open Educational Resources in Library and Information Science (LIS) within higher education institutions in the countries under the study scrutiny.*

RE: We appreciate very much this general introductory comment, where the reviewer states the relevance of the issue of critical assessments on OER use during COVID-19 pandemic, that in our opinion has not received the attention it deserves in the literature on Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT) during the pandemic. OER are the subject of much theoretical and descriptive literature analysing their characteristics and potential, promoting its use from a decontextualized perspective without considering the barriers and challenges to its adoption, but assessment of their actual use in university education falls short of expectations. This is one of the most interesting and surprising evidences resulting from our study of the COVID-19 period, which strongly suggested that their actual use was low and unsystematic, even in what seemed to be a very favourable situation such as the ERT. Hence, the reflections that teachers and students expressed a posteriori on this situation are relevant for detecting barriers and conditioning factors on which to act in the future for a more profitable use of the OER, as well as a greater involvement of teachers in their creation.

- **Comment #1:** *Reconsider the title of the paper since the significant data collected and utilized are related to the faculty members and students narratives and reflections on OER implementation during the COVID-19 contexts although the respondents were interviewed during the post-pandemic situation.*

RE: Since our study is related to both periods, COVID-19 (the focus of RQ 1 and RQ2) and Post COVID (RQ3) we have modified the paper title to clearly state we will deal with both periods. New title for version 2: Assessment of the use of Open Educational Resources at five European Library and Information Science higher education institutions **during and post COVID -19 pandemic**

- **Comment #2:** *Both the introduction and literature review sections would further benefit if the authors could substantially revise these sections with updated literature in the area under scrutiny.*

RE: We have updated the literature by searching more recent publications on our main topics. We have identified six references that provide some new ideas or approaches, which we have added in our literature review and discussion sections.

- **Comment #3:** *In so doing, please review past and recent literature that principally agrees with the widely accepted definition of OER rather than solely relying on UNESCO's (2019) definition. Consider, if there are any disagreements regarding the concept of OER over the years.*

RE: While there is no single definition of OER, the most recent UNESCO definition -included in the UNESCO OER Recommendation- is widely accepted: "OER are teaching, learning and research materials that make use of appropriate tools, such as open licensing, to permit their free reuse, continuous improvement and repurposing by others . . ." (Miao, Mishra, & Orr, 2019, p. 9). We have also reviewed some recent articles about OER and all of them used the same definition. That is why we have added it to the introduction. Also, we have linked the delineation of what defines an OER to a mention in the Conclusions Section, contextualising the low use of OER among our study participants.

- **Comment #4:** *The review section is poorly written and the line of reasoning for the current research is less than satisfactory. Please consider critically reporting the theoretical arguments and empirical research findings to set the broader context for the current research under scrutiny. This section could further benefit if the authors focus on reviewing literature in the areas associated with their research questions so that it would logically connect with the findings and discussion section. Moreover, the literature section seems to have abruptly ended, which looks very odd. I suggest that the authors summarize the literature review in a short paragraph and show the research gap that warrants further examination.*

RE: We have modified the literature review section to clarify the line of reasoning of the current research. Firstly, as we discussed above, we have updated the literature review with some recent publications that we identified on our main research topics. We have also structured the section, covering from global OER implementation initiatives to the specificity and key/differential areas of our contribution, i.e. a case of 5 higher education institutions in the discipline of Library and Information Science and Europe (as thematic and spatial context) and the teaching staff and students (as main actors).

- **Comment #5:** *In the methodology section, I wonder why the authors have not considered it important to give information about the participants, whether all of them belong to Library and Information Science or different departments. Unclarity about the details could further mislead the readers since the title of the paper and abstract are centered around this information. It is equally absent in the analysis section though the authors have mentioned this information in the discussion and conclusion section that the participants belonged to LIS.*

RE: We have clarified now that all interviewees (faculty and students) were from LIS Department/Faculty also in the Methodology and Analysis sections, as it has been suggested.

- **Comment #6:** *In the findings and analysis section, the paper could further benefit from a critical interpretation of data, which the paper hugely lacks in its current form. Also, I believe that the inverted commas in the quotes should be removed with the indentation*

the journal requires.

RE: Within the Discussion section, further critical interpretation of the data has been added, in order to connect the findings with other observed trends or recently emerging guidelines. As for the inverted commas, since we have followed all the editorial indications of ORE (and also performed at the final published versions by editing services from ORE), which has not indicated anything specific in this regard, we keep the text as it was - unless ORE expresses any new requirement.

- **Comment #7:** *Equally important concerns for me are that since the research has been based on fieldwork carried out in the LIS departments of the universities of Barcelona (Spain), Hildesheim (Germany), Osijek and Zagreb (Croatia) and the University of Library Studies and Information Technologies in Sofia (Bulgaria), there might be different experiences and perception of faculties and students toward OER based on their contexts. If authors have something interesting to share (probably not reported in the available literature as well as that has not been highlighted with clarity (compare and contrast) in the current study), I would encourage the authors to equally highlight these findings and discuss them. I believe that it would have a greater implication in the literature as well as guide future debates in the area.*

RE: In general, as far as the use of OER is concerned, the situation in the institutions with similar disciplinary traditions had similar characteristics. It is worth noting the differential case of Hildesheim (Germany) whose more digital orientation and specialisation in postgraduate course would explain a more intense and consolidated use of OER before COVID-19. But in general, for similar academic subjects, we have not actually identified many different perceptions of faculty and students towards OER depending on their context. In any case, for all the five institutions, the more digital oriented was the academic subject or the teacher background, the more likely OER could have some presence during the ERT and beyond. We have noted this adding a new text at the beginning of the Discussion Section.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 13 May 2024

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Fahriye Altinay

Near East University, Northern Cyprus, Turkey

Paper's title mentions the period of post covid 19 assessment but in the research questions first two of them are related to covid 19 period. Authors should state clear time period in relation to the focus of the study.

Significance of the study as a need for the study should be stated by updated references and it is essential to put importance to the key terms that makes this study different from others.

Results can be categorized based on research questions. Themes and codes can be created in the analysis in order to be more clarified in relation to the research focus.

Future projections and suggestions should be added for both research areas and researchers.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: online education, management, disability, strategic management, educational technology and quality

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Jul 2024

Cristóbal Urbano

We the authors greatly appreciate the reviewers' comments and time. Based on their suggestions, we will answer the reviewer's observations and revise our paper over the next few weeks to submit a new, corrected version. Some of the team members involved in this paper will be on holiday for a few weeks, so it will take some time. Thank you for your patience. Sincerely, Cristóbal Urbano, corresponding author

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Author Response 28 Aug 2024

Cristóbal Urbano

We welcome all comments and suggestions for improvement from reviewer 1. We consider them useful, and it is with great pleasure that we upload a revised version. The response to each comment is detailed below, together with the changes we have made to version 2 of the paper where appropriate (new text can be seen through the tracked changes):

Comment #1: *Papers title mentions the period of post covid 19 assessment but in the research questions first two of them are related to covid 19 period. Authors should state clear time period in relation to the focus of the study.* **RE:** Since our study is related to both periods, COVID-19 (the focus of RQ 1 and RQ2) and Post COVID-19 (RQ3), we have made a slight modification of the paper title to clearly state we will deal with both periods, like it is also stated in the abstract. New title for version 2:

- Assessment of the use of Open Educational Resources at five European Library and Information Science higher education institutions **during and post COVID -19 pandemic**

Comment 2#: *Significance of the study as a need for the study should be stated by updated references and it is essential to put importance to the key terms that makes this study different from others.*

RE: We have updated references by searching new publications on OER use and LIS during COVID-19 period (and post-pandemic) at the European context on OER assessment, the key and differential focus of our study. We have identified a few articles, from 2023 and 2024, that provide some ideas or approaches which we have added in our literature review and discussion sections.

Comment 3#: *Results can be categorized based on research questions. Themes and codes can be created in the analysis in order to be more clarified in relation to the research focus.* **RE:** The themes and codes presented in our study (and collected in Table II) are aligned with the general objectives of the DECriS project. Therefore, they are part of a broader study and have been designed from the same questionnaire script and from a first general analysis of the data, which considered a wide range of topics. For this reason, the coding was created in a general way and is not only categorized into OER research topics. As we consider that it is not appropriate to change the coding once the analysis is complete but, at the same time, we want to clarify the issue for readers (as the reviewer has pointed out) we have added a new paragraph in the Methodology section and we have adjusted Table II with tags in the first column to clarify. With this pair of changes, we aim to point out the connections between the general codes and our research themes and questions. We hope that this solution clarifies this issue.

Comment 4#: *Future projections and suggestions should be added for both research areas and researchers.*

RE: Since we agree to that proposal, we have added a final paragraph about further research on the issue of OER use.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.